

Analysis and Evaluation of Interfacial Delamination Energy of Notched Laminated Composites

I. Kimpara, I. Ohsawa

Department of Naval Architecture, University of Tokyo, 7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113, Japan

ABSTRACT

An interfacial delamination energy is introduced and formulated as a new delamination resistance parameter instead of the apparent interfacial strength itself, based on the energy consideration of a notched two-layered composite beam under pure bending. A new testing method is proposed on a four-point bending of a notched beam specimen to measure the newly defined interfacial delamination energy at any prescribed interface in laminated composites. The new parameter appears to be essentially independent of the test conditions of a notched beam specimen, which is thus regarded as a pseudo-material-constant unlike the apparent interfacial strength. The new technique is effectively applied to evaluate and compare the interlaminar delamination resistance between glass, carbon and glass/carbon hybrid laminates.

INTRODUCTION

The interlaminar shear and peeling strength, which are closely related to the interfacial bond strength, is much smaller than the inplane tensile, compressive and shear strength of fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) laminates. The author have noted that the interlaminar delamination plays an important role in the fracture of FRP laminates especially under impulsive loading, which is peculiar to inhomogeneous laminated composites. Hence the author have been motivated to devise some new impulsive testing methods in order to make a direct comparison between the dynamic interfacial strength of FRP laminates by applying an impact load and introducing a notch of a specimen in the direction in which only an interfacial delamination is forced to occur (1, 2, 3).

The apparent static interfacial strength, however, depends greatly on the test conditions on account of the stress concentration effect in notched specimens. Moreover it has been rather difficult to make a direct comparative evaluation on the delamination resistance at different interfaces in inhomogeneous laminates. In the present paper, an interfacial delamination energy is introduced and formulated as a new delamination resistance parameter to replace the apparent interfacial strength itself. The validity of the new parameter is examined based on a four-point bending of a notched FRP beam specimen. The new technique is applied to evaluate and compare the interfacial delamination energy at several kinds of interfaces in FRP laminates.

OBSERVATION ON BENDING FAILURE PROCESS OF FRP LAMINATES

It is well accepted that the effect of interfacial delamination can not be neglected on the energy absorption mechanism of FRP laminates under impulsive loading. However, it is also noteworthy that a static bending failure of FRP laminates is often accompanied with a marked interlaminar delamination. Typical observed failure modes are schematically classified in Fig.1 on an alternately-applied laminate of chopped strand mat (M) and woven roving (R) (abbreviated as a MR laminate) under a static three-point bending with the outer M layer on the tension side. A typical load-deflection curve is shown in Fig.2, in which the marks correspond to the failure modes shown in Fig.1. These failure modes are actually progressively observed as shown in Fig.3. The constitution of the specimen is as follows.

Glass constitution : R/MR/MR/M
 where R: woven roving (810 gf/m²),
 M: chopped strand mat (600 gf/m²),
 /: intermittent lamination in a hand lay-up method.

Matrix : unsaturated polyester resin.

Glass content : 41 wt% (mean).

The typical example shows that the load drops first when the outer M layer breaks which is then accompanied with the intermittent progress of delamination between the inner M and R. Hence, it can reasonably be expected that the interfacial delamination is first forced to proceed at a notch root when the notch is cut in the outer layer on the tension side of a laminated beam specimen under bending. The observation leads to a concept of bending a notched laminated beam to cause only a delamination.

Fig. 1 Typical fracture modes of a MR laminate under a three-point bending.
 (a) Tensile fracture of outer M layer (on tension side).
 (b) Delamination between outer M and inner R layer.
 (c) Buckling failure of outer R layer (on compression side).
 (d) Tensile fracture of inner RM layer.

Fig. 2 Typical load-deflection curve of a MR laminate under a three-point bending.

Fig. 3 Bending failure process of a MR laminate.

MODELIZATION OF INTERFACIAL DELAMINATION ENERGY

An interfacial delamination energy is introduced by the condition that a delamination starts at a notch root in a notched laminated composite, which is modeled based on a notched two-layered composite beam under pure bending as shown in Fig.4. A delamination is assumed to extend from the notch root A to the points B and C over the length, x , at a critical bending moment, M_{CR} , as shown in Fig.4. The bending rigidities of the individual beams 1 and 2 are, respectively, expressed by

$$\begin{aligned} D_1 &= (1/12)E_1bd_1^3 \\ D_2 &= (1/12)E_2bd_2^3 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

and the equivalent bending rigidity of the two-layered composite beam is given by the formula :

$$D_0 = \frac{bd_2^3d_1E_2E_1}{12(d_1E_1 + d_2E_2)} K \quad (2)$$

where E_1 and E_2 are the Young's moduli, d_1 and d_2 are the depths of the beams 1 and 2, respectively, b is the width of the beam and K is given by

$$K = 4 + 6(d_1/d_2) + 4(d_1/d_2)^2 + (E_1/E_2)(d_1/d_2)^3 + (E_2/E_1)(d_2/d_1) \quad (3)$$

Let the bending curvatures before and after the extension of delamination be κ , κ' , respectively, then

$$\kappa = M_{CR}/D_0, \quad \kappa' = M_{CR}/D_2 \quad (4)$$

The energy change due to the extension of delamination is expressed as follows (over the length x).

The increase in surface energy : $dU = bxR_{if}$ (R_{if} : interfacial delamination energy)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The decrease in strain energy of the beam 1 : } dU &= -(1/2)D_1\kappa^2x \\ &= -(1/2)(D_1/D_0^2)M_{CR}^2x \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The increase in strain energy of the beam 2 : } dU &= (1/2)D_2(\kappa'^2 - \kappa^2)x \\ &= (1/2)\{(1/D_2) - (D_2/D_0^2)\}M_{CR}^2x \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{The work done by the external moment : } M_{CR}(\kappa' - \kappa)x = M_{CR}(1/D_2 - 1/D_0)x$$

From the condition that the net change in total energy should be zero, the critical bending moment to start a delamination, M_{CR} , is given by the equation :

$$M_{CR} = (2bR_{if})^{1/2} / \{(D_1 + D_2)/(D_0^2) - (2/D_0) + (1/D_2)\}^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

or the interfacial delamination energy, R_{if} , is given by

$$R_{if} = (M_{CR}^2/2b) \{(D_1 + D_2)/(D_0^2) - (2/D_0) + (1/D_2)\} \quad (6)$$

Substituting the Equations (1), (2) and (3) into (5) and (6) gives

Fig. 4 Delamination of a notched two-layered composite beam under pure bending.

$$M_{CR} = (\sqrt{6}/6)bK(R_{if}d_2^3E_2)^{1/2}/[(1+1/\alpha\beta)(\alpha^3\beta+1) - 2K(1+1/\alpha\beta) + K^2]^{1/2}$$

$$R_{if} = (6M_{CR}^2/b^2K^2d_2^3E_2)[(1+1/\alpha\beta)(\alpha^3\beta+1) - 2K(1+1/\alpha\beta) + K^2] \quad (7), (8)$$

where, $\alpha = d_1/d_2$, $\beta = E_1/E_2$; $K = 4 + 6\alpha + 4\alpha^2 + \alpha^3 + 1/\alpha$

If the composite beam is regarded as homogeneous, let $E_1 = E_2 = E$, $h = d_1 + d_2$ (total depth of a beam), then, Eqs.(5) and (6) become

$$M_{CR} = (\sqrt{6}/6)b(R_{if}h^3E)^{1/2}/[(d_1/h)^3 + (d_2/h)^3 + (h/d_2)^3 - 2]^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

$$R_{if} = (6M_{CR}^2/b^2h^3E)[(d_1/h)^3 + (d_2/h)^3 + (h/d_2)^3 - 2] \quad (10)$$

FOUR-POINT BENDING OF NOTCHED LAMINATED BEAM

Testing Method

A four-point bending test of a notched laminated beam is proposed to start a delamination at a notch root by applying a pure bending as shown in Fig.5. The depth of a notch is chosen so that the notch root is attained at a prescribed interface and the inner span (l_2) is kept at $l_2 = 30$ mm, whereas the outer span ($l_1 = l - l_2$) is varied. The load is applied at a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. Acoustic emission (AE) is detected by a resonant-type AE sensor (140 kHz) attached to near the center of a specimen to monitor the start of delamination. The AE count rate is recorded simultaneously with a load-deflection curve on a X-Y recorder, as shown in Fig.6, through a discriminator and a rate/total counter (threshold level: 0.17 mV, gate time: 1 s, high-pass filter: $f_c = 100$ kHz, total gain: 40 dB).

The start of delamination is determined based on a proportional limit in a load-deflection curve or an initiation of AE count rate such as shown in Fig.6. The critical load to start a delamination is then decided to give the critical bending moment, which gives the interfacial delamination energy by Eqs.(8) or (10).

Fig. 5 Schema of notched four-point bending test.

Evaluation on Interfacial Delamination Energy

The interfacial delamination energy is evaluated by means of the notched four-point bending test on three kinds of interfaces in standard MR laminates. The dependency of the observed interfacial delamination energy on the test conditions is examined by varying the outer span as $l_2/h = 4, 6, 8$, and the depth of a notch as $d_1/h = 1/4, 1/2$. The start of delamination at a notch root is judged based on the proportional limit and the AE detection, which are comparatively examined.

The evaluated interfaces are as follows.

R interface : in a 15-ply laminate: R x 15, R: woven roving (800 gf/m²), mean glass content: 50 wt%, thickness: $h = 15.3$ mm, longitudinal Young's modulus: $E = 1,800$ kgf/mm².

Fig. 6 Load-deflection curve and detected acoustic emission.

M interface : in a 12-ply laminate: MRM x 4, M: chopped strand mat (600 gf/m²), R: woven roving (860 gf/m²), mean glass content: 35.8 wt%, thickness: h = 15.4 mm, longitudinal Young's modulus: E = 1,200 kgf/mm².

MR interface : in a 12-ply laminate: MR x 6, M: chopped strand mat (600 gf/m²), R: woven roving (860 gf/m²), mean glass content: 39.5 wt%, thickness: h = 14.4 mm, longitudinal Young's modulus: E = 1,300 kgf/mm².

The observed values are comparatively shown in Figs. 7, 8 and 9, respectively for the R, M and MR interfaces. The interfacial delamination energy appears to be essentially independent of the outer span and of the depth of a notch within the range of experiments. The parameter is, however, much underestimated based on the AE detection than the proportional limit, probably because the former is much more sensitive. The AE is essentially sensitive to a local damage in a high stress concentration region such as around a notch root, so that it needs to be further examined as a judgement standard for the start of delamination.

Fig. 7
Relation between observed interfacial delamination energy, outer span and depth of a notch in notched R x 15 laminates (R interface).

Fig. 8
Relation between observed interfacial delamination energy, outer span and depth of a notch in notched MRM x 4 laminates (M interface).

Fig. 9
Relation between observed interfacial delamination energy, outer span and depth of a notch in notched MR x 6 laminates (MR interface).

ACOUSTIC EMISSION ANALYSIS ON DELAMINATION

The acoustic emission is analyzed on a four-point bending of notched FRP laminates. Figure 10 shows a block diagram for instrumentation. The AE event counts are detected by the two AE sensors (150 kHz) attached to near the both ends of a specimen to measure the AE linear location through a distribution analyzer, while the AE ringdown counts are measured by the AE sensor near the center of a specimen to monitor the extension of damage around a notch root. The measuring conditions are as follows.

- AE event counts : total gain: 60 dB, band-pass filter: 100 - 200 kHz, threshold level: 0.5 mV, dead time: 0.3 ms.
- AE ringdown counts : total gain: 60 dB, band-pass filter: 100 kHz - 1 MHz, threshold level: 0.32 mV, gate time: 1 s, dead time: 0.19 ms.

Fig.10 Block diagram for detecting and analyzing AE.

Figure 11 shows a typical example for the change of AE event distributions due to the increase of load; Fig.12 is a typical CRT display. The change in AE distribution form appears to reflect the extension of delamination from a notch root, whereas the initial AE might be due to the local damage around a notch root. Figure 13 shows a typical recording of the AE ringdown counts with a load-deflection curve, in which a strain response is also shown measured by a strain gauge attached to near a notch root in the thickness-direction of

Fig.11 AE event distributions around a notch vs load.

Fig.12 AE linear location on a CRT display.

Fig.13 AE ringdown counts, thickness-direction strain and load vs deflection.

a specimen. It may be observed that there is an apparent change in the AE property around a load level corresponding to a proportional limit in a load-deflection curve, which is also roughly in accordance with the sharp rise in the thickness-direction strain response. Such an apparent point may be called "AE knee" here, which might be used as a judgement measure for the start of delamination.

The frequency analysis of AE signals is also made through a FFT; an example is shown in Fig.14 for typical MR interface. An apparent change may be observed in the AE waveforms and the AE frequency spectra before and after the "AE knee" or the proportional limit, which might support the above reasoning. Thus the "AE knee" could be used as a delamination judgement measure together with the proportional limit.

Fig.14 Change in AE waveforms and frequency spectra before and after the "AE knee".

COMPARATIVE EVALUATIONS ON INTERFACIAL DELAMINATION ENERGY AT VARIOUS INTERFACES

The interfacial delamination energy is comparatively evaluated on various interfaces in glass, carbon and glass/carbon hybrid laminates by means of the above technique. The outerspan-to-depth ratio of a specimen is chosen as $l_1/h = 6, 8$; the start of delamination is judged based on the proportional limit or the "AE knee" as described above. The kinds of prescribed interfaces are as follows; a special attention is directed to any difference between interfacial delamination resistance in primary and secondary-bonded interfaces.

MR interface (primary-bond) [A1] : $h = 15.0$ mm, d_1 : MR x 3 + M, d_2 : RM x 4, $E_1 = E_2 = 1,200$ kgf/mm², R: woven roving (810 gf/m²), M: chopped strand mat (600 gf/m²)

MR interface (secondary-bond) [A2] : $h = 14.8$ mm, d_1 : MRMRM, d_2 : R x 9, $E_1 = 1,000$ kgf/mm², $E_2 = 1,500$ kgf/mm², R: woven roving (860 gf/m²), M: chopped strand mat (600 gf/m²); after cure: 80°C x 5 hr, secondary-bonded after sanding.

CM interface (primary-bond) [B1] : $h = 15.4$ mm, d_1 : C x 4, d_2 : MR x 6 + M, $E_1 =$

3,500 kgf/mm², E₂ = 1,050 kgf/mm, C: "Torayca" cloth 6641B, R: woven roving (570 gf/m²), M: chopped strand mat (455 gf/m²).

CM interface (secondary-bond) [B2] : h = 16.0 mm, same as above ; after cure: 50°C x 8 hr, secondary-bonded after sanding.

R interface (primary-bond) [C] : h = 11.9 mm, R x 9, E₁ = E₂ = 1,500 kgf/mm², R: woven roving (810 gf/m²).

C interface (primary-bond) [D] : h = 14.9 mm, C x 18, E₁ = E₂ = 3,500 kgf/mm², C: "torayca" cloth 6641B.

Figure 15 shows some examples of sideview of delaminated interfaces. The comparison between observed interfacial delamination energy of the evaluated interfaces is summarized in Fig.16. It is found that the new parameter can effectively discriminate the expected difference between interfacial delamination resistance at primary and secondary-bonded interfaces. The "AE knee" criterion, however, gives a lower value of parameter than the proportional limit, although both are in the same tendency. Among the evaluated interfaces, a carbon interface [D] is shown to be lowest in the interfacial delamination energy.

(a) MR interface [A1]

(b) CM interface [B1]

Fig.15 Sideview of delaminated interfaces.

Fig.16 Comparison between interfacial delamination energy at various interfaces.

CONCLUSIONS

The interfacial delamination energy is effectively used as a new basic parameter to evaluate the interfacial delamination resistance of FRP laminates. A four-point bending test of notched FRP laminates is proposed the new parameter at any prescribed interface in laminates. The new parameter appears to be rather independent of the test conditions, so that it is especially useful in evaluating comparatively the interlaminar delamination resistance at different kinds of interfaces. However, the judging measure to detect the start of delamination should be further investigated.

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